

D6.5 Initial report on the contribution to standardization

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Executive summary

The deliverable D6.5 “Initial report on the contribution to standardization” is produced in the context of SunCoChem-WP6, Task 6.3 – Standardisation activities, in particular with regard to the subtask 6.3.2 “Contribution to the ongoing and future standardization developments”. This deliverable includes as main contribution the activities carried out until M24 to let the SunCoChem project transfer selected results to European or international standards. The transfer of SunCoChem results to standards being widely recognized by the industry and that are developed in a system external to the Consortium will ease the market uptake of these results and their impact beyond the duration of the project. Additionally, the standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel towards the stakeholders represented in the standardization committees.

D6.5 is based on the conclusions of two documents:

1. D6.2 “Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards”, made available at M6, that includes the information on the relevant existing standards and ongoing standardization projects of the relevant standardization technical committees to facilitate the use of existing knowledge and the compatibility and the interoperability of the results.
2. The document “Planning of the SunCoChem contribution to standardization”, made available at M20, defining the strategy of SunCoChem’s contribution to standardization. It included the steps to be taken for a successful contribution to standardization as well as the actions for its implementation and a tentative schedule. The document also provided with an update on new standards and projects of the relevant technical committees that were identified in D6.2 and included three new technical committees on photovoltaic energy systems and climate change.

D6.9 “Final report on the contribution to standardization” at M48 will summarize all the activities and results obtained in the context of the standardization activities.

The Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE), as a European Standardisation Body, is partner in the SunCoChem project to provide support regarding all the standardisation tasks included in the project.

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List of abbreviations

CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Standardisation in the Electrical field
CLC	
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
EN	European Standard
EU	European Union
ISO	International Standards Organisation
	International Standard published by ISO
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
	International Standard published by IEC
NMC	National mirror committee to a European or International standardization committee
NSB	National Standardization Body (UNE, DIN, AFNOR etc.)
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardisation/Spanish national standard
WG	Working Group
SC	Subcommittee

1. SCOPE

The Deliverable D6.5 “Initial report on the contribution to standardization” records the actions performed and the results of the interaction with the standardization system by M24. These interactions are addressed to the standardization committees previously identified by the means of document “Planning of the SunCoChem contribution to standardization” where the relevant stakeholders in the pertinent fields are represented. The objectives are to:

- Disseminate the results and objectives of SunCoChem using the network of the standardization community;
- Gather any feedback that may come from the standardization community regarding the development of SunCoChem;
- Facilitate the subsequent contribution to standardization allowing the related standardization committees an advance knowledge of SunCoChem and to comment about the standardization possibilities.

2. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE STANDARDIZATION STRATEGY

2.1 Strategy for the contribution to standardization

The contribution to standardization of SunCoChem is based on the interaction with the relevant Standardization Technical Committees and in the initiation of a standardization process. The strategy comprises the actions represented in Figure 1 which is taken from the document “Planning of the SunCoChem contribution to standardization”.

Figure 1 shows a linear progression of the steps shown on the left side of it. Whether all of these steps are actually carried out in a technical committee depends on various factors. First of all, a fundamental interest of the Technical Committee in the project should be mentioned here, without which none of the steps after making contact can be carried out. Furthermore, the current and planned projects of the Technical Committee play a role as well as the question to what extent the project results fall within the working area (scope) of existing Technical Committees.

Figure 1: Strategy for the SunCoChem contribution to standardization

2.2 First contact with standardization committees

2.2.1 General

The objectives of this first step are to raise awareness about SunCoChem among the relevant standardization committees and to ease subsequent contacts. Different categories of stakeholders at European/international level are present in the committees, so the

standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback will be asked to gather any view, opinion or advice about the project and the standardization possibilities or needs. Additionally, the first contacts will be useful to determine the best path towards the initiation of a standardization process and ease future contacts if this process is launched within a standardization committee.

At the SunCoChem General Assembly on 29 April 2021, the relevant areas for the further standardization activities were identified. The areas and the technical committees related to these are given in the table below.

Table 1 – Standardization committees relevant for further activities

Area	Technical committee	
Photocatalysis	CEN/TC 386	<i>Photocatalysis</i>
Solar energy	ISO/TC 180	<i>Solar energy</i>
	IEC/TC 82 and CLC/TC 82	<i>Solar photovoltaic energy systems</i>
Nano-technologies	ISO/TC 229	<i>Nanotechnologies</i>
	CEN/TC 352	<i>Nanotechnologies</i>
	IEC/TC 113	<i>Nanotechnology for electrotechnical products and systems</i>
Environment	ISO/TC 207	<i>Environmental management with focus on its subcommittee SC 7 Greenhouse gas management and related activities</i>
	ISO/TC 265	<i>Carbon dioxide capture, transportation, and geological storage</i>
	CEN/TC 467	<i>Climate Change</i>
	IEC/TC 111	<i>Environmental standardization for electrical and electronic products and systems</i>

The contact with the technical committees is done by e-mail to the secretariat of the individual technical committee. Before contact is made, it is analyzed how often a technical committee meets and whether an upcoming meeting has already been scheduled, so that this can already be referred to when contact is made. A typical first e-mail is shown below – it is the one that was sent to the secretary of CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”:

“Dear Ms Laoubi

My Name is Steffen Jenkel and I am representing UNE in the European Research and Innovation project SunCoChem - Photoelectrocatalytic device for SUN-driven CO₂ conversion into green CHEMicals. I would like to ask you whether it is possible to present the project at the next CEN/TC 386 plenary meeting?

The SunCoChem project aims to provide the chemical industry with an alternative to produce oxo-chemicals without using raw materials derived from carbon or oil. The project will develop a photoelectrocatalytic tandem reactor to manufacture valuable chemical oxo-products from renewable energies based on CO₂, H₂O and solar energy. This will be achieved by process

intensification, coupling a solar-driven CO₂ reduction to CO/H₂O oxidation to O₂ with C-C bond carbonylation reaction catalysed by novel multifunctional hybrid photoelectrocatalysts. Based on a single-unit CO₂ capture and conversion architecture to design a self-sufficient device, SunCoChem's innovation intends to reduce costs and CO₂ emissions, decreasing the dependence of the European Chemical Industry on carbon-based raw materials. More information can be found on <https://suncochem.eu/> and <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862192>.

I have seen that the last plenary just took place 24/25 June. Has the next plenary meeting been scheduled yet?

Thanking in advance and have a nice weekend.

Best regards

*Steffen JENKEL
Research and Innovation Unit
Spanish Association for Standardization, UNE”*

For the first contact, the focus is on the possibility of being invited to present the project directly to the Technical Committee at a plenary session. In this way, not only the stakeholders present but also all national standardization committees that are connected to the respective European or international technical committee are reached through the preceding and subsequent documentation (meeting agenda and meeting report including the presentation slides) and the project also will be subject of reporting at national level. In addition to the pure transmission of information, a presentation also allows initial feedback, a discussion and the linking of the project with individual actors, i.e., with persons for future contact and coordination. A possible exchange with representatives of the committee after a presentation also allows for an initial understanding of the committee's internal dynamics.

2.2.2 Results of first contact

With the exception of IEC/TC 82 and IEC/TC 111, UNE has already contacted the secretariats of the above standardization committees or subcommittees in order to ask for a possibility to present the project at a plenary meeting. The feedback received so far can be found in the Table 2.

Table 2 – Feedback received on first contact

Area	Committee	Response to first contact
Photocatalysis	CEN/TC 386	<p>Direct positive feedback and high interest in the project. Invitation to present SunCoChem at plenary meeting.</p> <p>At the suggestion of UNE, also interested in a presentation of the projects DECADE, FlowPhotoChem and Solar2Chem as well as the SUNERGY initiative.</p> <p>Presentation held by POLITO (Simelys Hernandez) and UNE (Steffen Jenkel) at the plenary meeting (online) on 22 March 2022.</p>

Area	Committee	Response to first contact
		<p>Provision of detailed information by UNE for the minutes of the plenary meeting.</p> <p>Interest in receiving input from SunCoChem to start future standardization work and future project updates.</p>
Solar energy	CLC/TC 82	<p>No interest in the project or a project presentation. It was offered to attend the plenary meeting on 17 March 2022 as guest without presentation. Since a Follow-up of the committee is carried out anyways, a participation without presentation was not done.</p>
	IEC/TC 82	<p>Still to be contacted</p> <p>CLC/TC 82 and IEC/TC 82 are closely related.</p>
	ISO/TC 180	<p>Direct positive feedback and interest in the project. Invitation to present SunCoChem at plenary meeting.</p> <p>ISO/TC 180 has not yet decided on the date (and place) of its next plenary meeting. It is expected to receive information during the summer months.</p>
Nano-technologies	CEN/TC 352	<p>Direct positive feedback and interest in the project. Invitation to present SunCoChem at plenary meeting.</p> <p>Presentation held by LAU (Mariajosé Lopez) and UNE (Steffen Jenkel) at the plenary meeting (online) on 22 March 2022.</p> <p>CEN/TC 352 asked how it can support the activities of SunCoChem, i.e., what kind of standards are missing.</p> <p>CEN/TC 352 is interested in receiving another presentation with further results of SunCoChem at a later stage.</p>
	ISO/TC 229	<p>No interest in the project or a project presentation. It was noted by the secretariat that the current TC 229 work programme is not connected to the activities of SunCoChem. A general interest in the Project is not given.</p>
	IEC/TC 113	<p>There was a general interest in the project.</p> <p>Upon request, the IEC/TC 113 secretariat was provided with further information regarding the application of nanomaterials in SunCoChem.</p>

Area	Committee	Response to first contact
		The project's content was considered as being too far away from the TC's scope so that a presentation was not desired by the secretariat.
Environment	CEN/TC 467	Interest in the project. Invitation to present SunCoChem at plenary meeting. Presentation held by EUT (Adrianna Nogalska) at the plenary meeting (online) on 22 March 2022.
	ISO/TC 207 /SC 7	Waiting for a final feedback. Proposal to present SunCoChem is under coordination.
	ISO/TC 265	Waiting for feedback
	IEC/TC 111	Still to be contacted

2.2.3 Analysis of the feedback of first contact

The project is generally met with interest from the standardization community. Already based on the deliverable D6.2 it could be shown that SunCoChem has a proximity to various standardization topics, but only very few committees (or their published standards) are directly relevant for the project activities.

The technical committees from the areas "Solar Energy" and "Environment" offer a very good opportunity to present the project to a diverse part of the standardization community in the context of the dissemination activities.

SunCoChem uses nanotechnologies, but there is only a slight connection to the activities of the two international committees, ISO/TC 229 and IEC/TC 113. The European committee CEN/TC 352 shows interest - however, SunCoChem still has to analyze how and to what extent further activities, which would go beyond a second project presentation but this time with updated project results, could be interesting and feasible.

CEN/TC 386 is certainly the closest in terms of content - photocatalysis. As expected, the project received the greatest and most intense response here. In section 2.4.4 more details on the coordination so far is described.

An analysis of the possibilities of a contribution to the ongoing and future standardization was carried out by means of a standardization workshop, see section 2.4.3.

2.3 Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

2.3.1 Follow-up of the activity of the relevant standardization committees

Monitoring the committees' activities is a continuous task throughout the project. A first update was given at the SunCoChem General Assembly on 29 April 2021. A second update is given

with Annexes A and B of the document “Planning of the SunCoChem contribution to standardization”.

An update on the remaining relevant technical committees will be given once per year in the context of a General Assembly meeting.

2.3.2 Further contact with the standardization committees

To date, there have been no further contacts with the Technical Committees that go beyond the explanations in Table 2.

In any case, when the time comes, the various committees that have already received a project presentation will be contacted in order to provide them with updated information and further project results.

With regard to CEN/TC 352 and in particular CEN/TC 386, some coordination must first be carried out within the consortium in order to then plan further cooperation.

2.3.3 Participation of SUNCOCHEM partners in standardization technical committees

Currently, no SunCoChem partner is participating in a standardization technical committee with relevance for the project at national, European or international level. This might change depending on the progress and detailed activities of the standardization process.

Annex A, section A.1 provides with an overview regarding the national standards bodies in the countries of the different SunCoChem partners and explains the general concept of the membership in a national standardization committee. This membership is one of the two possibilities for a participation of the work of a European or international technical committee and is not limited to the project lifetime.

2.3.4 Establishment of a project liaison of SunCoChem with standardization committees

The establishment of a project liaison can be an interesting and valuable solution for a direct contribution to standardization once it is decided that this contribution will be carried out via a specific technical committee. The motivation of such a project liaison can be given due to a specific planned contribution of SunCoChem that would fall under the scope of a Technical Committee that also showed interest to receive input from the project. Alternatively, a Technical Committee has ongoing or new standardization work for which a contribution could be given. See also Annex A, section A.2 for information.

At the moment, none of these two situations apply but it is possible that the coordination with CEN/TC 386 result in a project liaison.

2.4 Standardization process

2.4.1 General

The main objective of the standardization activities in SunCoChem is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring project results and findings to standards that will have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners, the results to go through a standardization process will be identified. Different options to contribute to standardization shall be considered depending on the kind of the results (nature, availability and IPR) and the standardization context (existence of closely related standards and feedback of the standardization committees). These options can be seen in Figure 1.

2.4.2 SunCoChem Standardization Workshop

On 21 February 2022, a project-internal Standardization Workshop organized by UNE was held. The minutes of the workshop as well as the presentations slides summarizing the results can be found in Annex B.

Four topics related to the objectives and activities of SunCoChem, for which a contribution to standardization might be prepared, were identified:

- evaluating/testing performance of photoelectron-catalysts for CO₂ reduction and water oxidation
- determination of targets characteristics for photocatalytic reactors/devices in order to progress in the development
- creation of a standard cell allowing a comparison of performance of different catalysts
- safety protocol for the construction of TPER

A further analysis of the topics is needed. It also needs to be analysed and coordinated among the SunCoChem partners to what extent confidential information is needed as an input. Related SunCoChem deliverables need to be linked with these topics as guidance for relevant content. UNE will send out a survey by email to have this linkage done. Working with content that will be provided in deliverables will make the preparation of content for a contribution to standardization a lot easier.

The Standardization Workshop was also used to prepare the information to be shared with the CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis” as well any requirements regarding a collaboration with the other two projects funded under the topic “CE-NMBP-25-2019 - Photocatalytic synthesis (RIA)” – FlowPhotoChem and DECADE.

The analysis of the CEN/TC 386 publications and projects showed that the activities of SunCoChem but also of DECADE and FlowPhotoChem address an advanced application of photocatalysis that are not yet covered in CEN/TC 386 standards or planned projects.

2.4.3 Cooperation with H2020 projects FlowPhotoChem and DECADE

In addition to joint dissemination activities (see T6.6 “Networking and clustering with other projects and initiatives”), cooperation with other projects that receive funding from the European Union under the topic “CE-NMBP-25-2019 - Photocatalytic synthesis (RIA)” can be interesting with regard to a broad and sustainable contribution to standardization. The cooperation can open up the possibility of making a contribution based on the experiences and requirements of different application situations of photo(electro)catalysis, in order to not only have an individual project situation as a starting point and input for standardization.

The interest of the SunCoChem project partners for a further collaboration with DECADE and FlowPhotoChem was confirmed at the GA in November 2021. The contact with the coordinators of both projects then took place in January 2022. The coordinators were also invited to present their projects to CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”. The possibility to do so was coordinated with the secretariat of CEN/TC 386 in advance.

On 9 March 2022, a meeting between Mr Pau Farras, coordinator of FlowPhotoChem, Mr Gabriele Centi, coordinator of DECADE, Simelys Hernandez from POLITO and Steffen Jenkel from UNE took place to prepare the presentations to CEN/TC 386 but also to generally discuss the interest to collaborate regarding a contribution to standardization. Neither DECADE nor FlowPhotoChem deploy dedicated standardization activities, nevertheless, the dissemination to the standardization community is planned. Only SunCoChem has a standards body as partner. At the meeting, the four topics (see 2.4.2) for a possible contribution to standardization were presented and discussed.

At the moment, there is interest in a collaboration. However, the current progress does not yet allow any concrete statement about further activities that goes beyond the presentation of the projects given to CEN/TC 386. Nevertheless, the cooperation has great potential, since the two coordinators are also connected to the Solar2Chem (Mr Farras is the project coordinator) project and the SUNERGY initiative. Thus, a large number of researchers and experts in the field of photo(electro)catalysis can potentially be reached and hopefully won over for participation in future standardization projects.

As soon as there is further clarity within the project about the further steps towards a contribution to standardization, the other projects will be informed, and further cooperation will be planned.

2.4.4 Presentation to CEN/TC 386 and received feedback

On 22 March 2022, SunCoChem together with the other H2020 projects DECADE, FlowPhotoChem and Solar2Chem as well as the initiative SUNERGY were presented to CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”. The presentation of SunCoChem was given by Simelys Hernandez from POLITO together with Steffen Jenkel from UNE. The presentation of FlowPhotoChem and Solar2Chem was given by Pau Farras and the DECADE project and the SUNERGY initiative were presented by Gabriele Centi.

An excerpt of the meeting agenda, the slides of the presentation of SunCoChem as well as an excerpt of the meeting minutes can be found in Annex C.

SunCoChem was presented last, so the Standardization Activities slides were presented last. The topics developed in the standardization workshop and discussed with PAU Farras and

Gabriele Centi for a possible contribution to normalization based on the results of the SunCoChem, DECADE and FlowPhotoChem projects were then discussed by those present. UNE explained the two options for a contribution to standardization - via a technical committee or via a workshop agreement (CWA).

CEN/TC 386 is very interested in integrating these new topics into the committee's work area. It was determined that the current scope of the TC does not yet provide for the use of photocatalytic processes for the use of solar energy for the production of chemicals.

In addition, the currently limited capacities of the CEN/TC 386 were mentioned. CEN/TC 386 is a comparatively small Technical Committee in terms of countries, experts and projects involved. SunCoChem, DECADE and FlowPhotoChem have been invited to present a concrete proposal for one or more new projects at the next plenary session of CEN/TC 386 (Spring 2023). CEN/TC 386 would then discuss this.

The following were identified as suitable topics for standardization within CEN/TC 386 considering that CEN/TC 386 focusses on the development of standardized test methods with the highest interest for the first two points:

- testing and evaluating the performance of photoelectron-catalysts for CO₂ reduction and water oxidation;
- protocols for testing photoelectron-catalysts to allow for benchmark for comparison of different materials;
- creation of a standard cell allowing a comparison of performance of different catalysts.

The determination of targets characteristics for photocatalytic reactors/devices in order to progress in the development in considered to be generally out of scope of standardization. And the development of safety protocols for the construction and handling of tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactors was considered to be out of scope of the CEN/TC 386 activities.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

Interaction with relevant standardization technical committees

SunCoChem has already been presented to three different technical committees and received positive feedback and was asked to present an update on its results at a later date. A commitment for two further presentations has already been received, but a date has yet to be coordinated. Regarding another committee, there is still no feedback and two other committees have yet to be contacted. Three further Technical Committees showed no interest.

Overall, the project is met with interest in the standardization community, whereby the interest of CEN/TC 386 is certainly to be emphasized.

Standardization process

The document “Planning of the SunCoChem contribution to standardization” was developed by UNE to guide the further standardization activities.

A project-internal standardization workshop was held to identify relevant topics for a contribution to standardization based on the project activities and the need for standardization seen by the partners. Several topics were identified.

CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis” was identified as technical committee with the highest potential for a contribution to standardization in the context of a technical committee due to its thematic proximity to the project activities.

SunCoChem together with further photo(electro)catalysis projects was presented to CEN/TC 386 and received very positive feedback. The projects were asked to provide with detailed proposal(s) for future standardization. The development of such proposal(s) will be coordinated by UNE.

Different paths can be chosen to develop the desired proposals, including the development of workshop agreements (CWA), which would already include the publication of a standard based on project results during the project period. The next steps still need to be coordinated within SunCoChem and the other projects.

Cooperation with other H2020 projects

The coordination and collaboration with related H2020 project show great potential with regard to the contribution to standardization but also with regard to linking the R&I community with standardization.

A first meeting with the coordinators of FlowPhotoChem and DECADE has been made to analyze the potential of a cooperation and to discuss the topics for a contribution to standardization as identified by the SunCoChem partners.

A joint presentation to CEN/TC 386 was made receiving high interest and showing the possibility to have a sustainable impact on new standardization projects.

SunCoChem will organize and promote the cooperation in order to put the contribution to standardization on a solid foundation in the best possible way.

Annex A

Direct participation in European or international standardization committees

A.1 Participation as individual partner

Participation in standardization work at European or international level requires **membership in a national mirror committee**, if this exists. The national mirror committee then sends experts to the working groups of the European or international committees or sends them as national delegates to technical committee plenary meetings. Each standards body has its own procedures, which mostly differ in details but basically reflect the principles on which standardization is based (among others: transparency, participation of all interested parties, consensus). Participation in a national committee can involve an annual contribution to costs.

Table A.1 – National standards bodies from partners' countries

Country	Logo	Name
France		AFNOR : Association Française de Normalisation (AFNOR: French Standardization Association)
Germany		DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V. (DIN German Institute for Standardization)
		DKE Deutsche Kommission Elektrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik in DIN und VDE (DKE German Commission for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies of DIN and VDE)
Greece		ΕΛΟΤ - Ελληνικός Οργανισμός Τυποποίησης (ELOT - Hellenic Organization for Standardization)
Italy		UNI - Ente italiano di normazione (Italian standardization body)
Netherlands		Koninklijk Nederlands Normalisatie Instituut Royal (Netherlands Standardization Institute)
Spain		Asociación Española de Normalización - UNE (Spanish Association for Standardisation - UNE)
Switzerland		Schweizerische Normen-Vereinigung (SNV) (Swiss Association for Standardization (SNV))

In Table A.1 the national standards bodies are given for the different countries in which the SunCoChem partners are located. Each country usually has a national standards body that is a member of the European standardization organizations. Germany is an exception here having two standards bodies.

If there is interest in active participation in European or international standardization work, UNE will assist in identifying the responsible national committee and in establishing contact.

Another possibility for active participation in standardization work is offered to European or international organizations or associations so that can apply for so-called **liaison status**. The liaison then exists directly between a European or international technical committee and the organization and allows experts to be sent to the working groups. Liaison organizations can also submit proposals for new standardization projects as well as comments on ongoing projects. Upon request, UNE will provide the information necessary to obtain a liaison status. These are generally publicly available. At the European level, the liaison status is linked to an annual contribution to costs.

A.2 Participation as R&I project via a project liaison

For R&I projects it is also possible to apply for liaison status to a European Technical Committee. Such a project liaison is a way of collaborating covered by CEN-CENELEC Guide 25. Following that Guide, a liaison can also be valuable when collaboration between an existing CEN/CENELEC Technical Body and a funded European R&I project is envisaged. In such cases, the Liaison status is limited to the duration of the R&I project.

The project in liaison is expected to provide high quality, added-value expertise in a defined technical field relevant for CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Bodies and to provide effective contributions through direct participation in their meetings. This collaboration can be focused on contributing to an ongoing work (drafting of EN, TS, TR), to the proposal of new ones or to the proposal for revising existing standardization deliverables.

The funded European R&I project requesting to participate in a CEN or CENELEC Body is granted the status of Liaison Organization through the appropriate procedures in accordance with the CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations Part 2.

Annex B

SunCoChem standardization workshop – minutes and presentation slides

B.1 Minutes

Minutes of the project-internal Standardization Workshop

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020- NMBP-ST-IND-2019 – 862192
Project title	SunCoChem: Photoelectrocatalytic device for sun-driven CO ₂ conversion into green chemicals
Duration of the project	May 2020 – April 2024 (48 months)
WP/Task:	WP7
Document date:	25 February 2022

Date and duration of the workshop:	21 February 2022, 10:00 until 12:30 h
Mode:	virtual
Participants of the workshop:	EUT: Maria Navarro POLITO: Alessia Fortunati, Hilmar Guzmán, Maddalena Zoli, Simelys Hernandez HZB: Babu Radhakrishnan IIT: Angelica Chiodoni, Sergio Bocchini SOL: Stephanie Narbey CNRS: Bamlak Setegne LAU: Mariajosé López Tendero AVT: Bart van den Bosch UNE: Steffen Jenkel

Background and motivation for the workshop

The standardization activities in SunCoChem extend over the entire duration of the project; based on the analysis of the relevant technical committees and their standards, the dissemination of the project to stakeholders involved in standardization and a contribution to standardization is planned and then implemented.

The results of the analysis of the existing standards were made available with D6.2 "Standardization landscape and applicable standards" at M6. Updated information was provided in M12 at the GA and by the means of Annexes A and B of document "Planning of the SunCoChem contribution to standardization" circulated at M20. The main part of the document "Planning of the SunCoChem contribution to standardization" explained the strategy for an effective and successful contribution based on SunCoChem results. UNE is preparing deliverable D6.5 "Initial contribution to standardization" to be ready at M24. For this deliverable, input is needed from the consortium to identify topics for a contribution to standardization.

Since summer 2021, relevant technical committees at European and international level have been contacted to present SunCoChem and to receive feedback on the project. March 2022 the project will be presented to the European committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis", which has the greatest thematic proximity to SunCoChem.

The internal Standardization Workshop was carried to identify ways how SunCoChem can contribute to standardization and to prepare the meeting with CEN/TC 386.

Discussed topics

1. Document "SunCoChem_Planning of the Contribution to Standardization"

The document was presented and explained by Steffen Jenkel by the means of the slides 3 and 4 of the attached presentation.

At the moment, a presentation of SunCoChem was already given to two technical committees on European level (CEN/TC 352 on Nanotechnologies and CEN/TC 467 on Climate Change). The project received general interest and was invited to present the progress to the committees again at a later stage.

The next presentation of SunCoChem will be given to CEN/TC 386 responsible for standards on photocatalysis, see below regarding item 3.

The possibilities for a contribution were explained and questions regarding how standardization can contribute were answered.

2. Identification of standardizable project findings

Following an explanation on typical subjects of standardization (processes, products and materials), see slide 5, standardizable project findings were identified. Several questions were discussed, see slides 6 to 8 for the questions and the answers.

Four topics related to the objectives and activities of SunCoChem, for which a contribution to standardization might be prepared, were identified:

- evaluating/testing performance of CO₂ reduction and water oxidation and photoelectro/electrocatalysts (project-specific testing protocols have been developed) – maybe a generalization can be done when comparing with other projects
- determination of targets characteristics for photocatalytic reactors/devices in order to progress in the development (this may also depend on project-specific objectives and requirements)
- creation of a standard cell allowing a comparison of performance of different catalysts
- protocol for the construction of TPER with regard to safety

A further analysis of the topics is needed. It also needs to be analysed and coordinated among the SunCoChem partners to what extent confidential information is needed as an input.

Related SunCoChem deliverables need to be linked with these topics as guidance for relevant content. UNE will send out a survey by email to have this linkage done. Working with content that will be provided in deliverables will make the preparation of content for a contribution to standardization a lot easier.

Further topics suitable for a contribution to standardization can be communicated to UNE at any time.

The above-listed topics will be also considered in the presentation of SunCoChem to CEN/TC 386 and for the coordination with the projects DECADE and FlowPhotoChem.

3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

The European technical committee was presented. The scope, the published standards and future projects were discussed. CEN/TC 386 so far does not include photoelectrocatalytic-related topics

The presentation of SunCoChem will be done by Simelys Hernandez.

The standardization activities within SunCoChem will be presented as well and based on the result of item 2 (see above) possible topics for a contribution to standardization will be coordinated with CEN/TC 386.

4. Preparation of session with DECADE and FlowPhotoChem

Together with SunCoChem, the projects DECADE, FlowPhotoChem and Solar2Chem will be presented to CEN/TC 386. This was organised by UNE. A preparatory meeting is to be organized with the coordinators of the projects DECADE and FlowPhotoChem (and Solar2Chem) to coordinate the presentations and maybe present ideas for a joint approach for a contribution to standardization.

During the workshop, similarities and differences between the projects were discussed.

At the session with the convenors, the possible topics for a contribution will be presented and the chance to collaborate on these will be analyzed.

Next steps

Steffen Jenkel will coordinate the preparatory meeting with the coordinators from DECADE and FlowPhotoChem (and Solar2Chem).

Simelys Hernandez will prepare the project presentation for CEN/TC 386.

Steffen Jenkel will prepare the presentation of the standardization activities for CEN/TC 386.

Steffen Jenkel will prepare a survey to identify relevant deliverables for the four topics.

All partners are asked to check whether further standardizable topics can be identified.

All partners are invited to get in touch with Steffen Jenkel, if they need the full versions of standards.

Attachment: Presentation slides of the Workshop

Minutes prepared by Steffen Jenkel, 25 February 2022

B.2 Workshop presentation with results

PhotoElectroCatalytic Device for SUN-Driven CO₂ conversion into Green CHEMicals

Project-internal Standardization Workshop

organized by UNE and held virtually on 21 February 2022

Slide 1

Structure of the Workshop

1. Document “SunCoChem_Planning of the Contribution to Standardization”
2. Identification of standardizable project findings
3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”
4. Preparation of session with DECADE and FlowPhotoChem

Slide 2

1. Planning of the contribution to standardization

1 st contact with standardization committees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of TCs to establish contact with - Content to disseminate - Planning
Interaction with standardization committees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow-up TC activities and update TC with the SunCoChem progress - Possible participation of SunCoChem experts via NSBs - Project liaison
Standardization process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Via TC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution to ongoing standardization work - Request for modifying an existing standard - Outline for a future standard / Development of new standard(s) - Via Workshop: Development of CEN Workshop Agreement (standard)

3

Slide 3

Contacted technical committees (TC)

Field	Technical Committee	Status/result
Nanotech	CEN/TC 352 "Nanotechnologies"	Presentation held at plenary, 7 October 2021, interest in a future presentation
Solar Energy	CLC/TC 82 "Solar photovoltaic energy systems"	Positive feedback, date for presentation to be coordinated
	ISO/TC 180 "Solar energy"	Positive feedback, date for presentation to be coordinated
Environment	CEN/TC 467 "Climate Change"	Presentation held at plenary, 13 December 2021, interest in a future presentation
	ISO/TC 207/SC 7 "Greenhouse gas management and related activities"	Positive feedback, date for presentation to be coordinated
Photocat	CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"	Presentation at next plenary meeting, 22 March 2022 (virtual)

4

Slide 4

2. Identification of standardizable project findings

2.1 Typical subjects of standardization

- **What is a standard?** Document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context

Standards should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits.
- **Examples** — *processes/methods*: how something has to be or should be done
 - *products and parts of it*: what requirements a product or parts of it has to meet, based on which characteristics a distinction between products have to be made, which tests have to be passed
 - *materials*: how they can be characterized, treated, tested, etc.
 - *services*: what does it contain, description and requirements of it

5

Slide 5

2. Identification of standardizable project findings

2.1 Typical subjects of standardization

- **What is a standard?** Document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context

Standards should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits.
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 - *services*: what does it contain, description and requirements of it

5

Slide 6

2. Identification of standardizable project findings

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Standards should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits.
- **Examples** — *processes/methods*: how something has to be or should be done
 - *products and parts of it*: what requirements a product or parts of it has to meet, based on which characteristics a distinction between products have to be made, which tests have to be passed
 - *materials*: how they can be characterized, treated, tested, etc.
 - *services*: what does it contain, description and requirements of it

5

Slide 7

2. Identification of standardizable project findings

2.2 Helpful questions with feedback from workshop participants (3)

- 5) In order to market the TPER in the future, do you think a standard may be useful?
→ *The current development stage (TRL) is too early for answering this question.*
- 6) Do you think any already developed or future SunCoChem deliverable could be interesting for being applied in the Photocatalytic synthesis or the Solar Chemicals sector as guidance or recommendations?
→ *The identification of those deliverables that are related to the four topics listed under question 4 will be done via a separate email asking all partners for support. In any case, confidentiality aspects have to be considered.*
- 7) Please tell if you deem any other information regarding your task/deliverables and standardisation relevant!
→ *No further feedback.*

8

Slide 8

3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

3.1 Scope of the Technical Committee (TC)

Photocatalysis is based on absorption of light and consequent production of oxidizing and reducing species both on the semiconductor and in the surrounding medium capable of partly or wholly mineralizing the majority of organic compounds. The oxidation state of inorganic compounds could be changed as well. Its principle is based on the simultaneous action of photons and of a catalytic layer which allows to destroy the molecules. The most commonly used photocatalyst is titanium dioxide (TiO₂), which is thermodynamically stable, non-toxic and economical. It can be used in powder form in water or deposited on a substrate (glass fibre, fabrics, plates/sheets,...).

Photocatalysis applications in the following sectors: air purification, water purification, self-cleaning application (surfaces: glass, metals, concretes, cements, plastics, ceramics, textiles, paints and varnishes, etc.), medical application, light sources (UV A, UVB, UVC, visible,...)

The objective is to introduce performance standards for photocatalytic effects (including photo induced effects).

The EN standards will mainly concern test and analysis methods.

9

Slide 9

3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

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Slide10

3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

3.4 Published standards

- CEN/TS 16599:2014, Photocatalysis - **Irradiation conditions for testing photocatalytic properties** of semiconducting materials and the measurement of these conditions
- EN 16846-1:2017, Photocatalysis - Measurement of **efficiency of photocatalytic devices used for the elimination of VOC and odour in indoor air** in active mode - Part 1: Batch mode test method with a closed chamber
- EN 17120:2019, Photocatalysis - **Water purification** - Performance of photocatalytic materials by measurement of phenol degradation
- EN 16845-1:2017, Photocatalysis - **Anti-soiling chemical activity** using adsorbed organics under solid/solid conditions - Part 1: Dyes on porous surfaces
- EN 16981:2021, Photocatalysis - **Glossary of terms**
- EN 16980-1:2021, Photocatalysis - **Continuous flow test methods** - Part 1: Determination of the degradation of nitric oxide (NO) in the air by photocatalytic materials

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Slide 11

3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

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Slide 12

3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

3.4 Published standards

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Slide 13

3. Preparation of the presentation of SunCoChem to European technical committee CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

3.7 Questions with answers (2)

- Is there any CEN/TC 386 standard that has been considered or even applied in SunCoChem? (Maybe CEN/TS 16599:2014, and the other future projects on artificial ageing?)
 - *No standard has been used so far. A general relevance is given for CEN/TS 16599:2014 (Irradiation conditions for testing photocatalytic properties) and EN 16981:2021 (Glossary of terms).*
- Is one of the ongoing or future projects relevant for SunCoChem or one of its partners? No
 - *The two projects (prEN 16980-2 and -3) are not of interest for SunCoChem. The two future projects (revision of CEN/TS 16599 and development of a standard on accelerated ageing) might be interesting but further information is needed.*

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Slide 14

4. Preparation of session with DECADE and FlowPhotoChem

4.1 Background

- At the next CEN/TC 386 plenary meeting (22 March 2022), SunCoChem will be presented together with the DECADE (<https://www.decadeproject.eu/>) project, the FlowPhotoChem project (<https://www.flowphotochem.eu/>) and the Solar2Chem project (<https://www.solar2chem.eu/>) to give CEN/TC 386 members a complete picture of the ongoing H2020 projects under topic "H2020 - CE-NMBP-25-2019 - Photocatalytic synthesis (RIA)" plus the thematically related H2020 Marie-Sklodowska-Curie project
- This has been organized by UNE after approval of the SunCoChem consortium
- The coordinators of the other three projects are interested and already confirmed their willingness to present their projects to CEN/TC 386. A preparatory meeting will be held but still needs to be organized
- A collaboration between SunCoChem, FlowPhotoChem and DECADE might also be interesting with regard to standardization. The mentioned preparatory meeting can also be used to identify overlaps, common objectives and activities. A position from SunCoChem is needed.

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Slide 15

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Slide 16

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Slide 17

4. Preparation of session with DECADE and FlowPhotoChem

4.3 FlowPhotoChem Project objectives

FlowPhotoChem - Integrated modular system for producing high-value chemicals

- The aim of FlowPhotoChem is to develop and model an integrated modular system based on continuous-flow heterogeneous photo(electro)catalytic reactors to produce relevant chemicals such as ethylene in the chemical sector, precursor to "green plastics" and many other high-value chemicals using abundant resources such as water, carbon dioxide and light.
- FlowPhotoChem aims at delivering cost-efficient small-scale systems for intermittent operation to respond to the needs of rural, isolated territories, and distributed manufacturing.
- Novel multifunctional photo(electro)catalytic materials integrated into practical and scalable reactors are required in Europe to maintain the technological leadership in chemical manufacturing, while ensuring the deployment of sustainable processes which meet circular economy and green industry for a low-carbon future.
- FlowPhotoChem will use the expertise of the partners to design, model, construct and validate an integrated modular system with improved energy efficiency and negative CO₂ emissions, since concentrated CO₂ will be valorised to high-value chemicals.

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Slide 18

4. Preparation of session with DECADE and FlowPhotoChem

4.3 Relation between DECADE, FlowPhotoChem and SunCoChem

- Are there thematic points of contact between SunCoChem and the two projects?
- What does SunCoChem and the other two projects have in common?

→ Up to now, there has been no exchange of information or a deeper insight in the project activities that goes deeper than the information provided in the course of presentations given so far (e.g., EU Green Week). From the project descriptions and objectives, the projects have in common topics like CO₂ conversion, water oxidation, energy sources, creation of a device and TRL5 as target.

- Are there fundamental differences? If yes, which? Do these impede a collaboration in standardization?
 - There are no fundamental differences, but the projects have differences.
- Do you think that a collaboration with regard to the development of technical standards on topics related with photocatalysis is possible? What might be topics for that?
 - In general, yes. It has to be coordinated to what extent a contribution to the four topics identified under 2.2, question 4 (slide 7) is of interest for the other two projects and whether they are willing to share information.

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Slide 19

PhotoElectroCatalytic Device for SUN-Driven CO₂ conversion into Green CHEMicals

A project coordinated by:

eurecat

Slide 20

Annex C

Presentation of SunCoChem to CEN/TC 386 “Photocatalysis”

C.1 Agenda of the CEN/TC 386 plenary held on 22 March 2022

Draft agenda of the plenary meeting (2022-03-22)

1	Opening of the meeting (9:00)	
2	Roll call of delegates	
3	Adoption of the draft agenda and minutes of the last plenary meeting	Documents N290 and N 296
4	Discussion on TC or SC chairperson	
4	Appointment of the Decision Drafting Committee	
5	Report of the Secretariat	
6	Reports of CEN/TC 386 Working Groups	
6.1	Report of CEN/TC 386/WG 1 "Terminology" by Claudio MINERO	
6.2	Report of CEN/TC 386/WG 2 "Air purification" by Chantal GUILLARD	
6.4	Report of CEN/TC 386/WG 6 "Light Sources" by Georges ZISSIS	
6.5	Report of CEN/TC 386/WG 7 "New technologies and other important issues" by Frantisek PETERKA	
6.6	Report of CEN/TC 386/WG 8 "Microbiological Effects" by Sebastien VACHER	
7	Liaisons with other TCs or other bodies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CEN/TC 139 Paints and varnishes - CEN/TC 129/WG 6 "Glass in building" - CEN/TC 351 "Construction Products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances" - CEN/TC 352 "Nanotechnology" Information on ISO/TC 206/WG 9 "Fine ceramics - Test methods for photocatalytic materials" by Koji TAKEUCHI	
8	Any other business* Presentation of SC59N works on Performance of Air Cleaners by Pascal KALUZNY Photocatalytic synthesis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the H2020 SunCoChem project by Simelyz HERNANDEZ and Steffen JENKEL - Presentation of the DECADE project by Gabriele CENTI - Presentation of the FlowPhotoChem and Solar2Chem by Pau FARRÀS *If you want to propose and / or amend these various points, contact Mrs. LAOUBI at least 1 week before the meeting date	
9	Planning of the next CEN/TC 386 and CEN/TC 386/WGs meetings	
10	Approval of Decisions	
11	End of the meeting (planned 13:00)	

C.2 Project presentation given to CEN/TC 386

PhotoElectroCatalytic Device for Sun-Driven CO₂ conversion into Green Chemicals

Project presentation to CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis"

Simelys HERNANDEZ, POLITECNICO DI TORINO
simelys.hernandez@polito.it
 Steffen JENKEL, UNE
sjenkel@une.org

Date: 22nd March 2022

Slide 1

SunCoChem general overview

Development of a Photo-ElectroCatalytic device for solar-driven CO₂ conversion into Green Chemicals

- European project funded under the topic CE-NMBP-25-2019 - Photocatalytic synthesis (RIA)
- Grant agreement ID: 862192
- 4 years duration, from May 2020 to April 2024
- Budget: 6,7 M€, of which 6,6M€ funded by the EC
- 14 partners from 8 different European countries
- Coordinated by Eurecat, RTO from Spain
- Technically Coordinated by Politecnico di Torino, Italy.

2

Slide 2

Consortium

14 partners from 8 European countries

3

Slide 3

Exploitation Model

4

Slide 4

The European Chemical Industry

Research and development efforts needed for the transition towards a low-emission industry

- Currently, the European Chemical Industry strongly depends on carbon feedstock imports for energy and chemical manufacturing processes, which are based over 95% on the use of fossil fuels.
- The introduction of sustainable chemistry using renewable resources to exploit CO₂ for the production of chemical products brings an opportunity to an efficient use of resources and preservation of the environment.
- This will contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gases, in line with the commitments agreed in 2015 and 2021 United Nations Climate Change Conferences (COP21 & COP26).

30

gigatons of CO₂
emitted yearly

95%

Chemicals based
on fossil fuels

The Chemical Industry is the third largest greenhouse gas emitter in Europe, with over 30 GtCO₂ every year.

5

Slide 5

Solar-driven Chemistry

Direct and indirect ways by which renewable energy can be transformed into chemical energy

- Solar-driven Chemistry refers to a future scenario for chemicals production based on substitution of fossil feedstocks as energy source and raw materials.
- A key aspect is the creation of a short-term cycle of utilisation of renewable energy sources to produce chemicals and energy vectors.
- In a broader perspective, Solar-driven Chemistry is crucial for an already started transition to a new economic cycle in chemistry and energy production.

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Slide 6

Concept

Photoelectrochemical Reactor

Oxo-Products

Starting olefin

Target Oxo-products

Z-Scheme Design

7

Slide 7

Concept

Starting point:
Artiphycion Project Reactor

8

Slide 8

Workplan

9

Slide 9

Carbon-neutral production of energy and high-value chemicals

A competitive self-biased photo-electro-catalytic tandem reactor (TPER)

- SunCoChem aims to provide a sustainable alternative to produce traditionally fossil-based chemicals by using sunlight as an energy source and reusing CO₂ as a raw material in a circular economy approach.
- The project will develop a photo-electrocatalytic tandem reactor (TPER) to manufacture valuable chemical oxo-products from renewable energies based on CO₂, H₂O and solar energy in the presence of ionic liquids.
- The TPER will be validated in an industrial plant environment at the production facility of IFF for the conversion of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions from Dow plant, to produce three added-value chemicals.

SunCoChem will develop a self-biased photo-reactor to efficiently produce oxo-products from CO₂, water and sunlight.

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Slide10

Application of photocatalysis for the SunCoChem TPER solution

More efficient PEcats and PEC reactor (Challenges)

- SunCoChem will exploit new concepts and advanced designs to create novel multifunctional hybrid photo-electrocatalysts (PEcats) based on nanoparticles and nanostructured materials.
- These novel PEcats will offer the advantage of achieving bandgap engineering and a Z-scheme strategy for the effective visible light-driven conversion of CO₂ to CO and the CO carbonylation reaction to oxo-products without the necessity of an external bias voltage.
- We aim to develop low-cost, novel and more efficient PEcats with an extended sunlight absorption, improved activity and selectivity.
- Testing protocols will be developed for allowing the benchmarking of the performance results (photocatalytic activity, selectivity and stability).
- Developing a new design of scalable photo-electrocatalytic reactor for performing sun-light driven CO₂ capture and conversion in the same unit.

PHOTOCATALYSTS IN THE TPER COMPONENTS

Cu-based Metal-oxidenanoparticles in a tandem photocathode for CO₂ conversion to oxo-products.

BiVO₄-based nanostructures in hybrid Photoanode for water oxidation

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Slide 11

Standardization activities

Motivation for the application of standardization activities in R&I projects

- CEN and CENELEC do not participate directly in research and innovation projects, delegating this responsibility to their national members
- Linking the R&I community with the European and international standardization system to raise awareness of the potential of standardization in order to support the dissemination and exploitation of R&I project results by incorporating these results into new standards
- Benefit for R&I: Ensure compatibility and interoperability with what already exists in the market through standards and contribute to future standards based on the project results

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Slide 12

Standardization activities

Relevant standardization landscape and approach for a contribution to standardization

Standardization committees in the scope of SunCoChem:

- Photocatalysis: CEN/TC 386
- Solar/PV: ISO/TC 180, IEC/TC 82
- Nanotechnology: CEN/TC 352, ISO/TC 229, IEC/TC 113
- Environment: CEN/TC 467, ISO/TC 265, ISO/TC 207, IEC/TC 111

Interesting standards for SunCoChem from CEN/TC 386 "Photocatalysis":

- EN 16981:2021, Photocatalysis - Glossary of terms
- CEN/TS 16599:2014, Photocatalysis - Irradiation conditions for testing photocatalytic properties of semiconducting materials

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Slide 13

Standardization activities

Possible topics for a contribution to standardization

- Testing and evaluating the performance of CO₂ reduction and water oxidation of photoelectron-catalysts and electrocatalysts
- Protocols for testing photoelectron-catalysts and electrocatalysts to allow for benchmark for comparison of different materials
- creation of a standard cell allowing a comparison of performance of different catalysts
- determination of targets characteristics for photocatalytic reactors/devices in order to progress in the development
- Safety protocols for the construction and handling of tandem photo-electrocatalytic reactors (TPER)

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Slide 14

*PhotoElectroCatalytic Device for
Sun-Driven CO₂ conversion into Green
Chemicals*

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon
2020 research and innovation programme under
Grant Agreement No. 862192.

Thank you!

 www.suncochem.eu

 [@SunCoChem_EU](https://twitter.com/SunCoChem_EU)

 info@suncochem.eu

A project coordinated by:

eureca!

Slide 15

C.3 Excerpt from draft meeting minutes

"Photocatalysis"
CEN/TC 386

Date: 2022-03-22
Doc. Number: N 301

Assistant:
Antoine AUROUSSEAU
Direct line: + 33 (0)1 41 62 84 86
Antoine.aurousseau@afnor.org

Your contact:
Djida LAOUBI
Direct line: + 33 (0)1 41 62 82 35
Djida.laoubi@afnor.org

**Draft Minutes of the 15th
Plenary CEN/TC 386 Plenary
meeting via Zoom meetings**

15th plenary meeting held on 2022-03-22
Chairman: Pascal KALUZNY
Secretary: Djida LAOUBI

8.2 - Photocatalytic synthesis projects

Four EU-funded Horizon 2020 research and innovation projects were presented at the meeting:

- FlowPhotoChem and Solar2Chem presented by the coordinator of both projects, Mr Pau Farras from the University of Galway (Ireland),
- DECADE presented by the coordinator of the project, Mr Gabriele Centi from the University of Messina (Italy) and representing the European Research Institute of Catalysis, and
- SunCOChem presented by the technical coordinator of the project, Ms Simelys Hernandez from the Polytechnical University of Torino (Italy), and Mr Steffen Jenkel from UNE.

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The projects FlowPhotoChem, DECADE and SunCoChem all started in May/June 2020 with a duration of 4 years. The FlowPhotoChem project develops and models an integrated modular system based on continuous-flow heterogeneous photo(electro)catalytic reactors producing ethylene and other high-value chemicals using water, carbon dioxide and light. The DECADE project focusses on the development of a new PEC technology using alcohols and waste CO₂ as feed for the Production of chemical fuels. The SunCoChem project develops a tandem photoelectrocatalytic reactor that will use sunlight, water and CO₂ to produce three high-value chemicals. For each project the objectives and the innovative technologies were presented. The Solar2Chem project aims to train 15 new researchers in state-of-the-art concepts and techniques with a focus on physical sciences to research on hybrid devices for producing solar chemicals. It started in February 2020 with a duration of 4, 5 years. Further information about the projects can be found on their websites: www.flowphotochem.eu, www.solar2chem.eu, www.decadeproject.eu and www.suncochem.eu.

The projects are also interested in a joint contribution to standardization. Therefore, several topics regarding photo(electro)catalytic reactors, for which a contribution to standardization can be made based on the project results, were presented at the meeting. The topics were coordinated between the projects under the advice of UNE, the Spanish Association for Standardization, as member of the SunCoChem project and can be found at the end of the SunCOChem presentation. Besides the introduction of new photocatalysis aspects of into standardization it is also envisaged to support the R&I activities in this field through standards that provide for effective Innovation processes considering market needs. The projects are interested to share information and prepare documents as basis for standardization work within CEN/TC 386.